

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 1-Thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one

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The chemistry and wide range of pharmaceutical properties of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives have been cited in literature¹. In view of potential biological² activities of arylpyrazoles and pyrazolin-5-one, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some of these compounds as possible antibacterial agents.

The synthesis involves treatment of ethyl acetoacetate with different diazonium salts in the presence of sodium acetate to yield ethyl 2-arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrates. The latter compounds on treatment with thiosemicarbazide furnish 1-thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2a-h) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The spectral data revealed that these compounds exist in hydrazono form (structures 2a-h). The structure requires that the C=O group in position-5 should be in conjugation with C=N group. A strong band appeared at 1683 cm⁻¹. The presence of low frequency band may therefore be attributed to the conjugation of cyclic C=O group in position-5 with the C=N group. Tranner³ also attributed the

appearance of C=O bond at lower frequency for 3-phenylhydrazono-2,4-dione to conjugation of C=O group with C=N. Furthermore, lower carbonyl band may also be assigned to C=O group in position-5 due to its participation in intramolecular hydrogen-bonding with NH group. Hydrazono structure is further supported by nmr and mass spectral studies. The nmr spectra exhibit signal at δ 9.5 which could be assigned to the hydrogen-bonded NH group. The hydrazono structure is further supported by the fragmentation pattern of the mass spectra. The mass spectra of 2c showed molecular ion peak M⁺ at m/z 291 corresponding to molecular formula C₁₂H₁₃N₅O₂S. There was a loss of 59 mass units (-CS-NH) to give a peak at m/z 232 followed by loss of 107 mass units (OCH₃C₆H₄) to give peak at m/z 125. There was a peak of weak intensity at m/z 97 (CH₃C≡C-CO⁺NH=NH) and m/z 67 (C⁺O-C≡C-CH₃) due to subsequent loss of 28 and 30 mass units of N₂ and N₂H₂ respectively (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Biological evaluation : Four pyrazole derivative (2d, f, g, h) were screened for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *S. typhae* applying agar-plate diffusion technique³. Maximum inhibition was revealed by 2d (14.5 and 10 mm) against *S. typhae* and *E. coli* at 100 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration, while 2f-h showed moderate activity. No significant activity was displayed by these compounds against *S. aureus*

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) and Varian FT (400 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JeOL JMS-D₃₀₀ spectrometer.

Ethyl 2-arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate (1a-h): To the aryl amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of HCl (8 ml) and water (6 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice bath, a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.03 mol) was added. The diazonium salt solution was filtered into a cooled solution of ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.122 mol) in ethanol (50 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from EtOH/MeOH (yields 75–90%): **1a**, m.p. 42°, δ 1.5 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.5 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.7 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.4 (2H, q, OCH_2), 7.1–7.9 (5H, m, ArH and NH); m/z 247 (M^+-1), 204, 173, 130, 106, 90, 77; **b**, 63°, ν_{max} 3 400 (NH), 2 900 (CH_2), 1 500 cm^{-1} (NHN=C); **c**, 56°; **d**, 196°, ν_{max} 3 440 (NH), 2 900 (CH_2), 1 680 and 1 710 (C=O), 1 500 cm^{-1} (NHN=C); **e**, > 280°; **f**, 149°; **g**, 83°, ν_{max} 3 100 (NH), 2 900 (CH_2), 1 690 (C=O), 1 510 cm^{-1} (NH–N = C); **h** 94°; m/z 268 (M^+), 226, 194, 152, 127, 91, 77.

1-Thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (2a-h): To ethyl 2-arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate (0.002 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20

ml), a solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. It was then cooled and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from EtOH/MeOH (yields 65–82%): **2a**, m.p. 205°, δ 2.25 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.4 (2H, s, CS-NH_2), 7.1–7.55 (4H, m, ArH), 9.5 (1H, s, NHN=C), m/z 275 (M^+), 216, 125, 97, 67; **b**, 220°, ν_{max} 3 434 (NH), 1 683 (C=O), 1 590 (NHN=C), 1 105 cm^{-1} (C=S); **c**, 191°, m/z 291 (M^+), 232, 125, 97, 67; **d**, >280°; **e**, >280°; **f**, 228°; **g**, 215°; **h**, 222°, ν_{max} 3 378 (NH), 1 685 (C=O), 1 550 (NHN=C), 1 090 cm^{-1} (C=S), m/z 295 (M^+), 236, 125, 97, 67.

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